

ONE DAY-AHEAD FORECASTING OF MEAN HOURLY GLOBAL SOLAR IRRADIATION FOR ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS PURPOSES USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK MODELING

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Abstract

During the last decades, renewable energy sources (RES) have been established as one of the main solutions in coping with the future energy needs, without the negative effects caused by the use of fossil fuels. The exploitation of RES however, faces serious difficulties concerning the penetration limits in the electrical grid due to its stochastic and variable availability. One of the main parameters affecting the reliability of the RES system, compared to the local conventional power station, is the ability to forecast the RES availability for a few hours ahead. The main goal of this work is the forecasting of global solar irradiation (GSI) on an horizontal plane, in hourly bases, 24hours ahead based only on historical meteorological data and artificial neural networks (ANN) modeling techniques. For that purpose, appropriate meteorological data have been recorded on minute intervals by a meteorological mast installed in Tilos Island, Greece from 17/03/2015 up to 20/12/2015. According to the forecasting results, the coefficient of determination ranges between 0.500 and 0.851 as well as the root mean square error ranges between 0.065kWh/m² and 0.105kWh/m². Finally, the proposed forecasting ANN model shows a fairly good forecasting ability which is crucial for a better management of solar energy systems.

1 Introduction

The development as well as the investment in renewable energy sources (RES) is expected to increase over the next decades. The utilization of renewable energy offers a wide range of exceptional benefits. There is also a link between exergy and sustainable development. A sustainable energy system may be regarded as a cost-efficient, reliable, and environmentally friendly energy

system that effectively utilizes local resources and networks [1]. The exploitation of RES however, faces serious difficulties concerning the penetration limits in the electrical grid due to its stochastic and variable availability. In order to confront this problem, energy storage systems are essential for minimizing waste RES energy and maximizing RES penetration. Based on that concept, the ongoing European funded project “Technology Innovation for the Local Scale Optimum Integration of Battery Energy Storage (TILOS)” aims to demonstrate large-scale RES penetration through an optimum integration of wind-photovoltaic power station and advanced battery storage at Tilos Island in Greece. TILOS is a multinational European demonstration and research project with 15 participating enterprises and institutes from 7 European countries coordinated by the Lab of Soft Energy Applications & Environmental Protection of Piraeus University of Applied Sciences. One of the main parameters affecting the reliability of the RES system, compared to the local conventional power station, is the ability to forecast the RES availability for a few hours ahead (e.g. wind speed, solar irradiation, etc).

In a considerable number of works an attempt to forecast the wind speed has been done [2-5]. Simultaneously, the same attempt in order to forecast solar irradiation has been developed in numerous works [6-8]. The main objective of the present work is to forecast global solar irradiation (GSI) in an hourly base for the next 24 consecutive hours, using artificial neural network modeling.

2 Methodology

2.1 Artificial Neural Networks Topology

For the forecasting of the mean hourly GSI 24 hours ahead artificial neural networks modeling was applied. ANN are based on the structure and function of the human brain. Neurons are basic components of the

human brain. They are essential nerve cells which create a dense network. The first ANN models were introduced during the decades of 1940 and 1950 with the basic artificial neuron model of McCulloch and Pitts [9], along with the first ANNs training algorithm of Rosenblatt [10]. In the following decades the use of the ANNs showed significant decline, due to high computing power requirements, which were not available from the computers of that era. The recession was followed by regeneration of ANNs with the introduction of the Hopfield's model [11-12]. These are known as Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) ANN, which along with the training algorithm of back-propagation, proposed by Werbos [13], attract the interest of the scientific community again.

Fig.1 Typical artificial neural network architecture [14]

Figure 1 shows the architecture of a typical MLP artificial neural network as well as the training algorithm of back-propagation [14]. The first layer is the input layer with one or more neurons, depending on the number of necessary input data for the proper training of ANN. One or more hidden layers follow with a number of artificial neurons that are necessary for the processing of the input signals. Each neuron of the hidden layer communicates with all the neurons of the next hidden layer, if any, having in each connection a typical weight factor (Fig. 1). Finally, the signal reaches the output layer, where the output value from the ANN compares with the target value and the error is estimated. Thus, the values of the weight factors are appropriately improved and the training cycle is repeated until the error is acceptable, depending on the application.

2.2. Data Management and ANN development

The goal of this work is the prediction of the mean hourly GSI on an horizontal plane, 24hours ahead using historical meteorological data and ANN modeling techniques. More specifically, an MLP-ANN forecasting model was developed to predict the mean hourly GSI for the next 24 consecutive hours, every next hour of the day. This means that every single hour of the day, the developed forecasting model is able to forecast the mean hourly GSI for the next 24 consecutive hours and so on. As a result of this procedure is that during the 24 hours of a day, the

developed ANN model gives 24 forecasts and in each forecast predicts the mean hourly GSI for the next 24 consecutive hours.

For this purpose, mean hourly values of air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), relative humidity (%), barometric pressure (kPa) and GSI (kWh/m^2) are used. The aforementioned data have been recorded on minute intervals by a meteorological mast installed in Tilos Island. The meteorological data cover the time period from 17/03/2015 up to 20/12/2015.

For the appropriate ANN training the whole data set was divided into two different subsets. The first subset contains all the data from 17/03/2015 until 15/12/2015 and was used as the training data set. The second subset contains the data from 16/12/2015 up to 20/12/2015 (5 days). The second subset was totally “unknown” to the trained ANN forecasting model and was used for the validation of the forecasting ability of the developed ANN model.

Table I presents the input data which have been used during the training phase of the developed ANN forecasting model as well as the output data (targets), in our case the mean hourly GSI 24 hours ahead. It should be noted that the developed ANN forecasting model forecasts the 24 mean hourly GSI values for the next 24 consecutive hours simultaneously.

Table 1 Input and output data of the developed ANN forecasting model

Input Data (Input Layer)	Output Data (Output Layer)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The month of the year (1,2,3,...,12) The hour of the day (1,2,3,...,24) The mean hourly air temperature of the 24 previous hours The mean hourly relative humidity of the 24 previous hours The mean hourly barometric pressure of the 24 previous hours The GSI of the 24 previous hours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The mean hourly GSI for the next 24 consecutive hours (24 values)

2.3. Statistical Evaluation Indices

For the evaluation of the forecasting ability of the developed ANN model, appropriate evaluation statistical indices were used. More specifically, the mean bias error (MBE), the root mean square error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the index of agreement (IA) were calculated in each case respectively. The MBE represents the degree of correspondence between the mean forecast and the

mean observation. The MBE is used in order to describe how much the model underestimates or overestimates the observed data. Positive or negative values indicate over estimated or under estimated prediction respectively [15].

The RMSE is a commonly used measure of the differences between the predicted values by a predictable model and the real-observed values. The RMSE is used as a single measure that indicates the ability of the model prediction and has the same units with the predicted value. The smaller the numerical value of RMSE is the closer to the real values are the predicted values by the model [15].

The coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates how much of the observed variability is accounted by the estimated model [16]. The coefficient of determination is a number between 0 and +1 and measures the degree of association between two variables. The coefficient of determination is calculated according to the equation [17].

Finally, the IA is a dimensionless measure that is limited to the range of 0-1. If IA=0, that means no agreement between prediction and observation and if IA=1, that means perfect agreement between prediction and observation. In other words, if IA=0 then the forecasted values present a great difference-distance in relation to the corresponding observed values and if IA=1 then all of the forecasted values are strictly equal to the corresponding observed values (i.e. predicted value=observed value for every forecasted value for each one of the forecasted values-cases) [18].

3 Results

Initially, a statistical treatment of the hourly GSI recorded values during the measuring period in Tilos Island, Greece took place. Figure 2 depicts the Box & Whiskers diagram of the absolute minimum (MINRAD) absolute maximum (MAXRAD) and average (AVERAD) hourly GSI during the cold (Fig. 2a) and the warm period of the year (Fig. 2b). The cold period of the year includes the months October-April and the warm period of the year includes months May-September. According to Fig.2, it seems that during the day, for both the cold and the warm period of the year, there are not any significant variations between the minimum, maximum and average hourly GSI. This indicates that the available solar energy during the year at the specific location is stable without any great variations.

Figure 3 represents the typical intraday profile of the GSI for both the cold (Fig. 3a) and the cold period of the year (Fig. 3b). It is obvious and expected that during the warm period of the year the available solar energy is almost double than the corresponding during the cold period of the year. Furthermore, the standard deviation of the mean hourly GSI during the warm period of the year is less and almost the half in comparison with the

corresponding standard deviation during the cold period of the year.

Fig.2 Box & Whisker of the observed hourly GSI

Fig. 3 Typical intraday GSI profile

As mentioned above, the second subset contains the data from 16/12/2015 up to 20/12/2015 (5 days). The second subset was totally “unknown” to the trained ANN forecasting model and was used for the validation of the forecasting ability of the developed ANN model. Figure 4 shows the observed mean hourly GSI (kWh/m²) during the 5 evaluation days from 16/12/2015 up to 20/12/2015.

Fig. 4 Observed mean hourly GSI from 16/12/2015 up to 20/12/2015. Tilos Island, Greece

According to Figure 4, during the evaluation time period the days 16, 17 and 20/12/2015 seem to be typical sunshine days of December for the specific location. During the middle of the 18/12/2015 the sky is partly cloudy and furthermore, during the 19/12/2015 the sky was overcast for most of the day. For these days the developed ANN forecasting model forecasts the mean hourly GSI 24 hours ahead. Specifically, as mentioned above the proposed forecasting model is based on a dynamic procedure. In other words, every single hour of the day the developed ANN forecasting model is able to give prognosis of the mean hourly GSI for the next 24 consecutive hours. Therefore, during the day the model gives 24 forecasts for 24 consecutive hours i.e. $24 \times 24 = 576$ hourly forecasts of the mean hourly GSI.

Figure 5 represents the forecasted vs the observed mean hourly GSI values of the 5 evaluation days (16th to 20/12/2015). So, on 24:00 hour of 15/12/2015 the forecasting model gives its first 24 forecasting hours which means the whole next day 16/12/2015. On the next hour (01:00 hour of 16/12/2015) the model gives 24 consecutive forecasting hours for the rest 23 hours of 16/12/2015 as well as the first hour of the next day (01:00 hour of 17/12/2015) and so on (Figure 5a).

Table 2, depicts the values of the appropriate evaluation statistical indices in order the forecasting ability of the proposed ANN forecasting model to be evaluated. Taking into consideration the values of Table 2, the MBE is ranging between $+0.015 \text{ kWh/m}^2$ up to $+0.035 \text{ kWh/m}^2$ which indicates that there is a slight overestimation of the mean hourly GSI. Simultaneously, the RMSE is ranging between 0.065 kWh/m^2 up to 0.105 kWh/m^2 .

Fig.5 Predicted vs Observed mean hourly GSI values between 16th and 17/12/2015 (a), 17th and 18/12/2015 (b), 18th and 19/12/2015 (c), 19th and 20/12/2015 (d).

Furthermore, R^2 take values from 0.500 up to 0.851 which indicates that the proposed ANN forecasting model is able to explain about 50.0% of the variation of the data during the worst day of prediction (19th to 20/12/2015) and about 85.1% during the best day of

prediction (16th to 17/12/2015). Finally, the IA is ranging between 0.826 and 0.957 which indicates that in the most forecasted cases the value of the predicted mean hourly GSI is very close to the corresponding observed value.

Concluding and according to Table 2, during the first two forecasted days (16th to 17/12/2015 and 17th to 18/12/2015) the values of statistical evaluation indices present a very good agreement between the observed and the predicted mean hourly GSI values. In comparison with Figure 4, it is obvious that these two

days are sunny days and so the model has a perfect forecasting ability. When the proposed (hourly moving) forecasting model gives predictions closer to 18/12/2015 and especially closer to 19/12/2015 the forecasting performance gets worst. This is due to the fact that these are cloudy days and the model's prediction is based on an historical momentum-experience of clear days (the two previous days). Despite that, the forecasting ability remains at a good level of reliability. Finally, the worst performance is for the prediction from 19/12/2015 to 20/12/2015.

Table 2 Statistical evaluation indices

Interval of forecast	Number of consecutive forecasted hours	MBE (kWh/m ²)	RMSE (kWh/m ²)	R ²	IA
16-17/12/2015	576	0.015	0.065	0.851	0.957
17-18/12/2015	576	0.035	0.083	0.781	0.927
18-19/12/2015	576	0.055	0.102	0.689	0.860
19-20/12/2015	576	0.025	0.105	0.500	0.826
Total (5 days)	2304	0.033	0.090	0.701	0.902

4 Conclusion

The aim of the present work is the development of a forecasting model in order to predict the mean hourly GSI 24 hours ahead in an hourly bases. For that purpose, ANN modeling techniques were applied. The developed ANN forecasting model is able to predict the mean hourly GSI in a dynamic way. More specifically, predicts every single hour of the day the mean hourly GSI on a horizontal plane for the next 24 consecutive hours.

Concluding, the proposed forecasting ANN model shows a fairly good forecasting ability which is crucial for a better management of solar energy systems. The benefit of the proposed methodology is that the forecast is based only in historical-past meteorological data which are available in any time through the measuring system of the photovoltaic installation (meteorological mast). In any case, further investigation is required in order to achieve a better forecasting performance especially during cloudy days and generally during changes from sunny to cloudy days and vice versa. For this purpose, maybe the use of future values of meteorological parameters such as cloudiness of the sky through numerical weather prediction (NWP) models is required. Authors believe that a combination of the proposed methodology with NWP models is able to cover the needs for an efficient and adequate management of a photovoltaic farm.

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6 References

- [1] Hepbasli A.: 'A key review on exergetic analysis and assessment of renewable energy resources for a sustainable future', *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, 2008, **12**, pp. 593–661
- [2] Kiplangat D.C., Asokan K., Kumar K.S.: 'Improved week-ahead predictions of wind speed using simple linear models with wavelet decomposition'. *Renew. Energ.*, 2016, **93**, pp. 38-44
- [3] Bracale A. and De Falco P.: 'An Advanced Bayesian Method for Short-Term Probabilistic Forecasting of the Generation of Wind Power', *Energies*, 2015, **8**, pp. 10293-10314
- [4] Tascikaraoglu A., Uzunoglu M.: 'A review of combined approaches for prediction of short-term wind speed and power', *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, 2014, **34**, pp. 243–254
- [5] Wu, Y.K., Hong, J.S.: 'A literature review of wind forecasting technology in the world'. *Proc. Int. Conf. IEEE POWERTECH*, Lausanne, Switzerland, July 2007, pp. 504-509
- [6] Ayodele T.R., Ogunjuyigbe A.S.O., Monyei C.G.: 'On the global solar radiation prediction methods', *J. Renew. Sust. Energ.*, 2016, **8**
- [7] Kashyap Y., Bansal A., Sao A.K.: 'Solar radiation forecasting with multiple parameters neural networks', *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, 2015, **49**, pp. 825–835
- [8] Qazi A., Fayaz H., Wadi A., Raj R.G., Rahim N.A., Khan W.A.: 'The artificial neural network for solar radiation prediction and designing solar systems: a

- systematic literature review', *J. Clean. Prod.*, 2015, **104**, pp. 1-12
- [9] McCulloch W.S and Pitts W.: 'A logical calculus of ideas immanent in Nervous activity', *B. Math. Biophys.*, 1943, **5**, pp.115-133
- [10] Rosenblatt F.: 'The Perceptron: A Probabilistic model for information storage and organization in the brain. Cornell Aeronautical Laboratory. *Psychol. Rev.*, 1958, **65**, 6, pp. 386-408
- [11] Hopfield J.J.: 'Neural networks and physical systems with emergent collective computational abilities', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA*, 1982, **9**, pp. 2554-2558
- [12] Hopfield J.J.: 'Learning algorithms and probability distributions in feed-forward and feed-back networks', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA*, 1987, **84**, pp. 8429-8433
- [13] Werbos P.: 'Generalization of Backpropagation with application to a recurrent gas market model' *Neural Networks*, 1988, **1**, pp. 339-356
- [14] Caudill M., Butler C.: 'Understanding neural networks', Cambridge, MA:MIT Press, ISBN 0262530996, 1992.
- [15] Moustris K.P., Ziomas I.C., Paliatsos A.G.: '3-Day-Ahead Forecasting of Regional Pollution Index for the Pollutants NO₂, CO, SO₂, and O₃ Using Artificial Neural Networks in Athens, Greece', *Water Air Soil Poll.*, 2010, **200**, pp. 29-43
- [16] Kolehmainen M., Martikainen H., Ruuskanen J.: 'Neural networks and periodic components used in air quality forecasting', *Atmos. Environ.*, 2001, **35**, pp. 815-825
- [17] Comrie A.C.: 'Comparing neural networks and regression models for ozone forecasting', *J. Air Waste Manag. Assoc.*, 1997, **47**, pp. 653-663
- [18] Willmott C.J., Ackleson S.G., Davis R.E., Feddema J.J., Klink K.M., Legates D.R., O'Donnell J., Rowe C.: 'Statistics for the evaluation and comparison of models', *J. Geophys. Res.*, 1985, **90**, pp. 8995-9005